

Implementing the Sponge City Concept (SCC) in Gaborone: Lessons from China and Beyond

Marumo Kedumetse J. Marumo ✉

College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai, China P.R.;
UNEP-Tongji Institute of Environmental for Sustainable Development, Tongji University, Shanghai, China P.R

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Abstract

Gaborone, Botswana's capital city, faces an increasingly severe hydrological paradox—flooding during intense rains and water scarcity during dry seasons. This study explores the feasibility of implementing the Sponge City Concept (SCC) in Gaborone, drawing from China's extensive experience and successful pilot projects. Using a qualitative desktop review of academic literature, government reports, and climate data, the paper highlights how SCC principles such as water absorption, storage, purification, and reuse can be tailored to semi-arid urban environments. Case studies from China (e.g., Ningbo, Wuhan, Xi'an) and Kenya (Kitui) demonstrate the adaptability and effectiveness of green infrastructure in addressing urban flooding, water shortages, and ecosystem degradation. The findings indicate that SCC implementation in Gaborone could yield environmental, social, economic, and institutional benefits, including flood mitigation, improved water security, urban greening, and increased public health. However, challenges such as funding constraints, technical maintenance, and institutional capacity must be addressed through phased implementation, policy alignment, and community engagement. The study concludes that a localized SCC model could significantly enhance Gaborone's resilience to climate extremes and serve as a model for similar semi-arid cities in sub-Saharan Africa.

Keywords: *Sponge city, Gaborone, green infrastructure, water scarcity, urban flooding, climate resilience.*

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Introduction

The term sponge city has roots in early urban studies and population geography, particularly in the context of industrialization and urban growth in the West. Scholars used this metaphor to explain how urban centers acted as hubs of economic, social, and cultural activity, which, in turn, drew people from rural areas (Budge, 2006). In the context of China's urban planning, the term "sponge city" offers a striking metaphor that depicts the urban environment as a dynamic system capable of naturally absorbing, storing,

and gradually releasing water. This concept emphasizes the idea that cities, much like a sponge, can manage rainwater and storm water efficiently through innovative infrastructure and design (Liu et al., 2017). By incorporating features such as permeable surfaces, green roofs, wetlands, and urban forests, sponge cities are designed to reduce the risk of flooding, enhance water conservation, and improve overall environmental sustainability (Liang et al., 2020).

The "sponge city" concept focuses on creating urban landscapes that mimic natural processes, allowing rainwater to be absorbed by the ground,

stored in reservoirs, and then slowly released back into the environment or used for other purposes, such as irrigation or water supply (Guan et al., 2021). According to Qiao et al., (2020) rapid population growth, urbanization, and intensive infrastructure development have led to the replacement of permeable green spaces with impermeable surfaces, causing poor drainage and heat dissipation and that contributed to more frequent urban flooding and the worsening of the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect. As a result, in 2013, during the China Central Work Conference on Urbanization, President Xi Jinping introduced the "sponge city" concept. This initiative represents a new approach to urban development aimed at effectively managing urban rainwater (Liu et al., 2017).

By integrating sustainable drainage systems, rainwater harvesting technologies, and ecological restoration techniques, sponge cities aim to reduce the reliance on traditional, hard infrastructure like concrete drainage systems, which can often exacerbate flooding and environmental degradation. Ultimately, the goal is to make cities more resilient to the impacts of climate change while improving urban livability and fostering a more harmonious relationship between urban spaces and the natural environment. This paper explores the experiences of China in implementing Sponge City projects, the lessons learned from these efforts, and the potential for replicating these practices in other parts of the world.

While this model was initially applied in humid urban regions to address flooding and water pollution, its principles are increasingly being adapted to semi-arid environments, where water scarcity and sporadic rainfall patterns dominate (Liu et al., 2022). In such settings, sponge city strategies prioritize water conservation, rainwater harvesting, and efficient storm water management. Semi-arid cities like Gaborone can benefit from interventions such as permeable pavements, vegetated swales, rain gardens, green roofs, and decentralized water storage systems, which enable the capture and reuse of limited rainfall (Bigurra-Alzati et al., 2020). These adaptations not only reduce flash flood risks during sudden storms but also contribute to

groundwater recharge, enhance urban biodiversity, and mitigate heat stress. Localizing sponge city principles in arid contexts supports climate-resilient urban infrastructure, ecological sustainability, and improved water security.

Sponge City Model

This concept integrates sustainable infrastructure and natural systems to create cities that are more resilient to the challenges posed by climate change, urbanization, and resource depletion. The core principles that define the Sponge City design are integral to ensuring effective water management in urban environments, and each of these principles plays a crucial role in maintaining ecological balance while enhancing urban livability. These core principles are:

Water Absorption

One of the primary features of Sponge Cities is the use of permeable materials that allow rainwater to infiltrate into the soil, reducing runoff and minimizing the need for traditional drainage systems. These materials include permeable pavements, green roofs, and vegetated surfaces, which absorb rainwater instead of allowing it to flow into storm water systems (Wang et al., 2017). The promotion of urban greenery, such as parks, wetlands, and urban forests, also helps absorb rainwater and reduce the heat island effect, making cities more sustainable and comfortable for inhabitants. Permeable surfaces also contribute to groundwater recharge, which is essential in areas facing water shortages (Scholz & Grabowiecki, 2007).

Water Storage

To manage heavy rainfall and prevent flooding, Sponge Cities incorporate innovative storage solutions that can hold excess water during periods of intense precipitation. These include underground reservoirs, retention ponds, and artificial wetlands that store water temporarily before it can be either absorbed into the ground or treated for reuse (Hermaputi & Hua, 2017). Such storage systems play a crucial role in mitigating the risk of urban flooding by providing a buffer to capture storm water. Moreover, these systems enhance the urban

landscape and biodiversity by creating habitats for plants and animals.

Water Purification

Sponge Cities also emphasize natural water purification methods. The integration of constructed wetlands and vegetative filtration systems helps to clean storm water before it is discharged into natural water bodies. Vegetation in these systems acts as a biofilter, removing pollutants such as heavy metals, sediments, and nutrients, which can degrade water quality and harm aquatic ecosystems (Zheng et al., 2021). By filtering rainwater naturally, Sponge Cities improve water quality, reduce contamination risks, and support the restoration of local ecosystems. Additionally, these systems enhance urban aesthetics by integrating nature into the urban environment, providing green spaces that benefit both humans and wildlife (Alikhani et al., 2021).

Water Reuse

Another key principle of Sponge Cities is the promotion of water reuse. Collected rainwater is stored and repurposed for non-potable uses such as irrigation, cooling systems, and landscape maintenance, reducing the demand on potable water supplies. This practice not only conserves valuable water resources but also ensures that urban areas remain resilient during periods of drought or water shortages (Nguyen et al., 2019). Additionally, encouraging the use of reclaimed water for industrial processes or even toilet flushing can help reduce the strain on municipal water systems. By adopting water reuse practices, cities can move towards a more circular water economy, where water is continuously recycled and reused within the urban environment (Liu et al., 2021).

Early Case Studies Demonstrated the Efficacy of SCC

Ningbo's implementation of the Sponge City program under the "Blue-Green City" concept has produced notable environmental, social, and urban revitalization outcomes. By integrating green infrastructure and restoring natural hydrological cycles, the city has effectively reduced flood risks, improved water quality, and

enhanced sustainability (Wang, 2023). Key initiatives include the use of urban forests, natural waterways, and wetland systems for rainwater harvesting and purification, particularly in regions like Ningbo Eastern New Town, where previously polluted rivers have been restored into ecologically functional systems. These measures have also mitigated the urban heat island effect, reduced traffic noise, and created public recreational spaces, significantly improving urban livability. Furthermore, the revitalization of degraded land through terraces and wetlands has not only enhanced biodiversity but also turned former problem areas into valuable community and ecological assets.

By 2018, Wuhan, China, had successfully implemented 389 sponge city projects as part of its pilot program under the national "Sponge City" initiative. These projects incorporated green infrastructure measures such as permeable pavements, rain gardens, constructed wetlands, green roofs, and bio-retention systems to manage stormwater sustainably and reduce surface runoff. As a result, the city achieved a remarkable 38% reduction in flood-prone areas, significantly mitigating urban flooding risks that had long plagued low-lying neighborhoods. In addition to flood control, the initiative contributed to substantial improvements in water quality, with many previously polluted urban rivers showing measurable declines in contaminants due to natural filtration and ecological restoration efforts. Furthermore, enhanced groundwater recharge was facilitated through increased infiltration, helping to stabilize aquifer levels and improve long-term urban water security. These outcomes not only advanced urban resilience but also promoted ecological and aesthetic enhancements in public spaces, thereby contributing to overall urban livability and climate adaptation (Ding et al., 2017).

A compelling case study of sponge city implementation in a semi-arid environment is the city of Xi'an, located on China's Loess Plateau. Characterized by severe seasonal rainfall variation and acute water shortages, Xi'an undertook sponge city development to address both urban waterlogging and resource scarcity.

Using the Storm Water Management Model (SWMM), seven green infrastructure renovation scenarios ranging from green roofs and rain gardens to permeable pavements and their combinations were simulated. Results revealed that the combination of all three elements (green roof, rain garden, and permeable pavement) achieved the most effective reduction in total runoff, peak flow, and comprehensive runoff coefficient. This optimal design reduced total runoff by nearly 59% and peak flow by over 63% during simulated storm events. The annual available rainwater in Xi'an's urban area, estimated at approximately $1.42 \times 10^8 \text{ m}^3$, was found to nearly match the city's public water consumption, highlighting the strategy's strong potential for urban water reuse. However, challenges such as loess soil collapsibility, limited effective rainfall, and structural risks near buildings underline the need for localized planning and technical adaptation (Liu et al., 2022).

Kitui County in Kenya implemented a unique adaptation of the sponge city concept tailored to its semi-arid conditions through the 'Sponge Towns' pilot project. This initiative, launched as part of a broader effort to enhance urban climate resilience and water security, focused on cost-effective, nature-based solutions. Key interventions included the installation of rainwater harvesting systems on public and private buildings, the construction of infiltration trenches along roadsides, and the development of green streets that incorporate vegetation and soil systems to absorb stormwater. These measures not only reduced surface runoff and the occurrence of flash floods, particularly during short and intense rainfall events, but also contributed significantly to local water availability. Captured rainwater was stored for later use in domestic and agricultural applications, easing the pressure on limited groundwater resources. Additionally, the project enhanced urban aesthetics and provided green spaces for the community, encouraging environmental stewardship. The Sponge Towns model demonstrates how sponge city principles can be effectively localized to arid and semi-arid regions, offering valuable lessons for other

water-scarce municipalities across Africa and beyond (Aqua for All, 2018).

Materials and Methods

This study adopted a desktop review methodology to gather, assess, and synthesize information relevant to the feasibility and implications of implementing the Sponge City Concept (SCC) in Gaborone. The research relied entirely on secondary data sources without the collection of new primary data.

A wide range of documents was reviewed, including:

Peer-reviewed journal articles on urban water management, sponge cities, nature-based solutions (NBS), and semi-arid climate adaptation.

Government and institutional reports concerning water scarcity, urban flooding, and climate resilience in Botswana.

International case studies on SCC projects, particularly from China and Kenya, illustrating diverse climatic adaptations.

Grey literature, including conference proceedings, NGO reports, and technical guidelines on green infrastructure practices.

Climate data specific to Gaborone from reputable sources such as the Botswana Meteorological Services and global climate databases.

The desktop review was conducted using a qualitative content analysis approach. Sources were evaluated for relevance, credibility, and applicability to the urban and climatic context of Gaborone. Major themes and patterns were identified, particularly regarding challenges, implementation strategies, anticipated outcomes, and barriers to SCC adoption.

Comparative analysis was also used, drawing lessons from SCC adaptations in other semi-arid cities to propose context-specific recommendations for Gaborone. No empirical fieldwork, stakeholder interviews, or surveys were performed; thus, the findings are interpretive and based on the synthesis of available literature.

Results

Gaborone's Urban Hydrological Challenges

Figure 1. Map of southern Botswana showing areas affected by severe flooding in mid-February 2025, including Gaborone and surroundings (blue shades indicate rainfall/flood extent). In this event, torrential rains (200+ mm in 5 days) caused rivers like the Segoditshane in Gaborone to overflow, inundating low-lying suburbs

Source: worldweatherattribution.org;
global-flood.emergency.copernicus.eu

Gaborone, the capital city of Botswana, faces severe hydrological challenges, which are primarily manifested at two extremes: frequent urban flooding during intense rainfall events and chronic water scarcity during dry periods. The challenges can be summarized as follows:

- 1. Urban Flooding:** High-intensity storms during the summer rainy season often overwhelm Gaborone's drainage systems, many of which are undersized or poorly maintained. Rapid urban expansion has exacerbated the problem, increasing impervious surfaces like roads, parking lots, and rooftops, which generate fast runoff (Lee, 2023). As a result, flash floods occur in low-lying neighborhoods and along river channels, damaging property and disrupting daily life. For instance, in February 2025, Gaborone experienced catastrophic flooding when approximately 160 mm of rainfall was recorded in just 24 hours, causing the Segoditshane River to overflow and inundate

homes and businesses (global-flood.emergency.copernicus.eu). The city's exposure to flooding has been exacerbated by urban expansion into natural floodplains, and the impact of such events is heightened due to inadequate drainage systems.

- 2. Water Scarcity:** In contrast to flooding, Gaborone also endures persistent water shortages, particularly during drought periods (Toteng, 2008). The city's primary water source, the Gaborone Dam, often fails to fully replenish during drought years, leading to water rationing. Additionally, the semi-arid climate results in high evaporation losses from reservoirs, further complicating water availability. Although the city has diversified its water sources by utilizing the North-South Carrier (NSC) pipelines, which transport water from northern reservoirs, upstream catchment degradation and insufficient rainfall continue to strain water availability.

These challenges highlight Gaborone's dual hydrological dilemma: excess water during heavy rains and insufficient water during droughts.

Feasibility and Implementation Opportunities in Gaborone

Implementing the **Sponge City Concept (SCC)** in Gaborone is feasible through a phased approach that integrates with the city's ongoing urban development plans. Several opportunities exist to introduce sponge features into the city, from retrofitting existing infrastructure to planning new developments with green design principles. Some of the key opportunities include:

- 1. Enhancing Natural Drainage Corridors:** The Segoditshane River could be rehabilitated into a more naturalized river park with widened vegetated buffers or detention basins. This would help manage floodwaters more effectively by allowing them to spread and infiltrate naturally.

- 2. Transforming Open Spaces:** Many open spaces and undeveloped plots in Gaborone can be transformed into rain gardens or small wetland parks. Additionally, community playgrounds and sports fields could be adapted

as detention basins to store stormwater temporarily.

3. **Rainwater Harvesting:** The city's residential and commercial areas offer significant potential for retrofitting with rainwater harvesting systems. Encouraging households and businesses to install rooftop catchment systems and storage tanks can help alleviate pressure on the municipal water supply and reduce surface runoff.

4. **Permeable Surfaces:** Updating building and zoning codes to encourage the use of permeable pavements and green roofs could mitigate runoff and reduce the impact of urbanization on stormwater management. Permeable pavements can be especially beneficial in parking lots and driveways.

5. **Institutional Coordination:** Effective implementation will require coordination between various agencies such as water, planning, and roads. Public awareness campaigns and local involvement are crucial for the success of these initiatives.

Anticipated Outcomes of SCC Implementation in Gaborone

If the **Sponge City Concept** is implemented, several positive environmental, social, economic, and institutional outcomes are anticipated:

1. Environmental Outcomes:

- Reduced urban flooding due to decentralized stormwater capture systems.
- Improved groundwater recharge, supporting well water and stream baseflows (Alikhani et al., 2021).
- Enhanced water quality in rivers, as green infrastructure such as wetlands will filter out pollutants from runoff before it enters water bodies.
- Mitigation of the urban heat island effect by increasing green spaces, shade trees, and water features.
- Increased biodiversity and carbon sequestration, fostering a resilient urban ecosystem (Li et al., 2020).

2. Social Outcomes:

- Increased public safety and comfort during heavy rains, as streets are less likely to flood (Wang, 2023).
- Improved public health due to reduced exposure to waterborne diseases and mosquito breeding grounds.
- A more pleasant and green urban environment, contributing to stronger community well-being.
- Increased public awareness and participation in water conservation efforts.

3. Economic Outcomes:

- Cost savings from avoided flood damage, which can be substantial in the long term (Yu et al., 2023).
- Reduced water supply costs due to rainwater harvesting and efficient stormwater management.
- Job creation in the landscaping, horticultural, and maintenance sectors due to the implementation of green infrastructure.
- Enhanced property values and the promotion of eco-tourism due to the beautification of urban areas.

4. Institutional Outcomes:

- Stronger collaboration between various departments/institutions, fostering more integrated urban water management (Vinagre et al., 2025).
- Potential for Gaborone to become a national model for sustainable urban development, inspiring other cities in Botswana and beyond.
- Improved governance through greater community involvement in maintaining green infrastructure (Everett et al, 2021).

Challenges and Limitations

While the prospects of the Sponge City Concept are promising, several challenges and limitations must be acknowledged for Gaborone:

Financial Constraints: Implementing SCC infrastructure citywide can be expensive initially

(Ding et al., 2017, Liang, 2018). Constructing wetlands, retrofitting drains, installing tanks require upfront investment (Gachango et al., 2015). Gaborone's city budget may be limited, and external funding would be needed. There is also economic uncertainty in quantifying returns on these green investments. Traditional cost-benefit analysis might undervalue benefits like ecosystem services, making it tricky to justify projects purely on financial terms (Oppio et al., 2024). Innovative financing (grants, public-private partnerships) and phasing will be necessary. Maintenance funding is another concern – unlike one-off construction of a drain, green infrastructure needs ongoing care, and securing budget for continuous maintenance of many small sites can be difficult (Su et al., 2020).

Maintenance and Sustainability: Sponge city features require consistent maintenance to function optimally. Plants need care, sediment must be removed from ponds, permeable pavements must be kept clear of clogging debris (Chan et al., 2018, Ren et al., 2017). In Gaborone, where maintenance of existing drainage is already a challenge, adding green systems could strain the capacity of municipal services. There's a risk that without proper upkeep, swales could fill with trash or invasive weeds, negating their benefits. Moreover, many SCC components could be on private or community property, making it harder for city authorities to monitor and maintain them. Ensuring long-term stewardship possibly by engaging local communities or via public education is essential, but that takes effort and behavior change (Su et al., 2020). Another sustainability issue is water availability for vegetation; during multi-year droughts, planted areas might wither unless drought-hardy species were used. Planning for worst-case dry scenarios (even if it means some features lie dormant) is necessary so that the system bounces back when rain returns.

Technical and Climatic Challenges: Local soil and climate conditions might limit certain sponge techniques. For example, if some areas have clayey soil with poor infiltration, typical rain gardens won't percolate well and could become waterlogged mosquito-breeding pits (Halecki & Stachura, 2021). In such spots, engineered

solutions like sub-surface drains or alternative measures are needed. Gaborone also occasionally sees extreme events beyond design assumptions – an exceptionally rare downpour might overwhelm even well-designed sponge features, so conventional emergency infrastructure (spillways, channels) cannot be completely eliminated (Li et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020). High evaporation in hot months is a challenge; open ponds could shrink quickly, and green roofs might dry out without irrigation. Designers must avoid solutions that effectively “waste” water or require too much supplemental watering (Ma, Ning, & Jiang, 2024). Additionally, water quality could be a challenge: the first heavy rain after a long dry spell can flush a lot of pollutants off urban surfaces. If not managed, this could contaminate groundwater. Implementing pretreatment (like vegetative filter strips) is a technical must. Finally, Botswana sometimes experiences multi-year drought cycles– during such times, SCC infrastructure will get little use (since it won't rain to activate them), which could lead to neglect or repurposing unless their value is understood (Mao et al., 2024).

Community Acceptance and Institutional Barriers: Transforming parts of the city into sponge features may face social and administrative hurdles. Some residents or developers might resist changes like converting open land into wetlands or using space for detention basins, perceiving it as losing developable land (Li et al., 2020). Land availability in urban areas can be limited, and setting aside plots for green infrastructure might conflict with other development goals (Zhang et al., 2019). Educating stakeholders about the long-term benefits is crucial to overcome “grey infrastructure bias.” There may also be cultural preferences for neat, concrete solutions over what could be seen as messy natural ones – for example, a grassy swale versus a concrete curb. Overcoming this mindset requires demonstration projects to show that vegetated systems can be attractive and effective. Within institutions, lack of capacity or interdisciplinary cooperation could impede implementation (Zuniga-Teran et al., 2020). If city engineers are not familiar with designing bio-retention or if

maintenance crews lack horticultural skills, initial implementation might falter. Training and perhaps bringing in external expertise in green infrastructure design will be needed (Owojori & Erasmus, 2025; Kanade & Batule, 2024). Legal or regulatory frameworks might also lag behind; building codes and drainage standards may need revisions to formally incorporate SCC measures, and this bureaucratic process can be slow (Ding et al., 2019). Lastly, climate uncertainty looms as an external limitation: climate change could alter rainfall patterns in unknown ways – either more intense storms or longer droughts – and the SCC design must be robust and flexible enough to handle a range of future conditions, which is challenging to predict (worldweatherattribution.org, Wang & Foley, 2023).

While no insurmountable barrier has been identified, the above challenges mean that implementation of the Sponge City Concept in Gaborone must be strategic and adaptive. Financial planning, community engagement, technical customization, and strong institutional commitment will be key to ensuring the longevity and success of sponge city initiatives. Recognizing these limitations early allows planners to incorporate mitigation strategies (e.g. dedicated maintenance funds, pilot testing, capacity building) as part of the project design.

Discussion

The Sponge City Concept (SCC) provides a sustainable and integrated solution to Gaborone’s dual hydrological challenges: urban flooding during heavy rains and chronic water scarcity during dry periods. Although originally developed for humid climates, the SCC model is flexible and adaptable to semi-arid regions, such as Gaborone. The city's climatic pattern, characterized by highly seasonal rainfall—450–510 mm annually, with the majority of precipitation falling between November and March—creates a paradox of water extremes (Van Wyk et al, 2012). Summers bring intense downpours and high temperatures (25–30°C), while winters are dry and mild (Sun & Marschner, 2018). This rainfall pattern poses significant challenges for water management, exacerbated by rapid urban growth, increased

impervious surfaces, and underdeveloped drainage systems that heighten vulnerability to flash floods and water shortages (World Weather Attribution, 2025; Kgweetsi, 2025).

Figure 2. Climate graph of Gaborone, Botswana, illustrating mean monthly rainfall (blue bars, in mm) and temperature (red line, in °C)

Source: Climate-Data.ORG

Gaborone's current water management system struggles to cope with these extremes. Urbanization has led to increased runoff during heavy rains, overwhelming traditional drainage systems, while the city's reliance on the Gaborone Dam and additional pipelines from northern reservoirs cannot fully address the long-term water scarcity exacerbated by evaporation and catchment degradation. These challenges underscore the urgency of finding a resilient, climate-responsive solution.

The Sponge City Concept offers a promising strategy by employing nature-based solutions such as rain gardens, permeable pavements, and constructed wetlands. By adopting these measures, Gaborone can reduce flood risks, enhance groundwater recharge, and improve overall water security. The use of deep infiltration systems, drought-tolerant landscaping, and semi-arid resilient constructed wetlands is especially crucial in adapting the SCC model to Gaborone’s unique environmental conditions. These interventions can help manage the heavy rainfall in short bursts while also capturing and storing water for use during dry spells, effectively balancing the city's water extremes.

While the potential benefits of SCC are substantial, several challenges need to be

addressed for successful implementation. Financial constraints pose a significant barrier, as the upfront costs of building and retrofitting infrastructure such as green roofs, bio-swales, and retention basins can be high. However, the long-term benefits—reduced flood damage, improved water supply, and enhanced public health—offer strong justification for investment. Innovative financing models, including public-private partnerships and climate resilience grants, will be essential to overcoming this obstacle.

Moreover, the maintenance and sustainability of green infrastructure is another critical challenge. To ensure the effectiveness of SCC, it will require ongoing care, such as the removal of debris from permeable pavements, maintaining vegetation, and cleaning sediment from constructed wetlands. Gaborone's municipal services are already stretched in terms of maintaining current infrastructure, so integrating green infrastructure will necessitate coordinated efforts across agencies. Engaging the community in maintaining these systems, through public education and active participation, will be crucial to their success.

Institutional capacity and community acceptance will also play pivotal roles in the success of SCC. Effective implementation will require strong coordination among municipal departments such as water, planning, and roads and local communities. Public awareness campaigns and educational initiatives on the benefits of green infrastructure can foster a sense of ownership and stewardship, ensuring long-term maintenance and sustainability. Demonstrating the benefits through pilot projects, which could focus on flood-prone neighborhoods, will be essential in gaining broader community and institutional support.

Additionally, climatic factors present specific challenges for the SCC in Gaborone. The city's semi-arid conditions, with high evaporation rates and long dry spells, mean that water retention and infiltration systems must be designed to minimize water loss. Open water features such as ponds and wetlands may require deeper basins, shading, and drought-resistant vegetation to prevent water evaporation. There may also be

issues with water quality, as the first rainfall after a dry period can wash pollutants into the stormwater system, which will require pre-treatment measures to ensure the water remains usable.

Conclusion

Gaborone faces a complex hydrological dilemma, with both severe flooding and water scarcity challenges. The Sponge City Concept provides a comprehensive, adaptive solution that addresses both issues by capturing and storing stormwater for reuse, while reducing flood risks and enhancing urban green spaces. Although challenges such as financial constraints, maintenance, and technical limitations exist, the potential benefits of implementing SCC in Gaborone reduced flood risks, improved water security, and enhanced public health make it a compelling strategy.

Recommendations for Gaborone's future water management strategy include:

- Developing a phased implementation plan for SCC, starting with pilot projects.
- Integrating SCC measures into urban development policies and zoning codes.
- Engaging local communities in the planning and maintenance of green infrastructure.
- Securing funding through innovative financing models, such as public-private partnership.

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Conflict of Interests

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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